

Gezi - 10 Years After, Maxim Gorki Theatre, 26 May - 25 June, 2023

Gezinema World Cinema Documentaries

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Co-curated by Şirin Fulya Erensoy and Necati Sönmez

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Screening: My Imaginary Country, 2022, Patricio Guzmán

Protests that exploded onto the streets of Chile's capital of Santiago in 2019 as the population demanded more democracy and social equality around education, healthcare and job opportunities.

Q&A Session with Patricio Guzmán (zoom), and Lena Ulbricht, moderated by Şirin Fulya Erensoy and Necati Sönmez. Spanish-English translation by Bárbara Lázara, photographs by Monica Segura

Lena Ulbricht is a Chilean-German academic and activist. She has a PhD in political science and is a researcher at the WZB Berlin Social Science Center Berlin and at the Weizenbaum Institute for the Networked Society. She has been active in various Berlin based networks in support of the social uprising in Chile in 2019-2021. Her research topics are the societal implications of digital technologies, power theory and feminism. She co-hosts PurpleCode, a podcast about intersectional feminist perspectives on digital societies.

NS: Patricio Guzmán is one of the best documentary filmmakers of our era, not only in Chile or Latin America, but in the world. All of his films are about the last 50 years of the history of Chile. He preserved the memory of a country and probably the whole continent. His most famous film is "The Battle of Chile," which was in the making for 5 years. It is a trilogy made in the second half of the 1970s, providing an account of Chile during the Allende times and the coup d'état. Another well-known film of his is "Nostalgia for the Light," which explores the lasting impacts of Augusto Pinochet's dictatorship and then he made a film that examines the fate of two persecuted groups - the indigenous peoples and the victims of Pinochet called "The Pearl Bottom," and finally, we have his last film: "My Imaginary Country." I would like to say: Hello, welcome, Mr. Guzmán... (clapping)... and the producer of his film is with us as well, so I will pass the word on to my colleague for the first question.

ŞE: Thank you all for being here, Mr. Guzmán, Renata, thank you also for joining us. Barbara will be translating my questions into Spanish and Mr. Guzmán's responses as well.

As a first question, there is this one sentence in the film that made me think a lot about the Gezi Park protests in Istanbul from 2013. It is: "Transportation fees have risen and this caused a spark which later put the country on fire." I keep thinking about how in Gezi, the trees also were the spark that later led to the uprising, so it was just this excuse to come together against growing authoritarianism, limits on freedom of expression, and so forth. I know you were not in Chile at the time, but were you surprised by the events and the revolt that began in October 2019? What was your immediate response? Let's say when you heard of what was happening, did you feel that there was this atmosphere beforehand?

PG: I was not in Chile at the time, but for me, it was a great surprise and the feeling that I needed to go to Chile immediately. Beforehand, I was in Turkey, so I could witness this great movement with enormous enthusiasm and a feeling that

everything would be changing afterwards.

LU (Q): Why did you decide to film the movie just before the referendum and not wait to get the results of the referendum before finishing the movie?

PG: That is a very good question. Nevertheless, when you make a documentary you have to have a final, you have to make a decision to end the film. We thought after the referendum, we have a new cycle so this would open a new, or another chapter, which could be very entangling in the documentary so we decided to end it in this cycle.

NS: I would like to go back to your previous films and put them next to each other and ask: during these past 50 years, did your reflection on documentary filmmaking, or filming struggles of revolutions, change? Because you began with filming the first revolution, which ironically happened after the election, not the war or struggle, while now we see a country in flames. Actually, the demands of this second revolution are for basic rights while the first one was about changing the systems fundamentally. The question is whether you compare these two revolutions in terms of the demands of the public?

PG: They are very, very different and interesting. In the first revolution, Allende was such a clear leader for the people and it had such an enormous power for the people, and the contra-revolutionary violence, there were lots of deaths, and Pinochet in power wanted all the Chileans to flee from Chile. Here it is very different. This is more about: let's imagine how a revolution could be because the mass movement was so impressive and so big, but we do not know what is going to happen with this, we are still in expectation as to what this is going to bring to the people.

ŞE: Mr. Guzmán, I was curious about your role as a filmmaker and also as a political actor, or at least someone - when looking at your filmography we know that you have had a personal stake where you were politically involved - here you are more an observer rather than a participant and you are communicating with a younger generation of political activists. How is that experience for you?

PG: In reality, I was never a professional politician but an observer at that time. I was not a militant. Of course, in *The Battle of Chile*, I showed that I was a sympathiser of Allende but I feel that to make a documentary, you have to be more objective and not be so enthusiastic about your own politics because you have to observe, look, and describe. This is your role as a filmmaker. My point of view is also: of course, I am going to show that I sympathise with Allende, but I am not going to ignore the enemy because we have to be concerned about the enemy. That's why I was showing a lot of opinions of the Pinochet sympathisers.

Mario Rizzi: I come from a country that has not worked out its history, as you refer to with the dictatorship in Chile. I come from Italy and now it is paying its consequences with its new government. We have a two-thirds majority of the right-wing in parliament, although only 15% of the people voted for them in reality. This is the result of the majority system in parliament and the fact that people do not go to vote... I am saying all this as a premise because the first character of your film was underlining that most people are not coming from a political party - as was the case in Gezi - that most people were not politically affiliated and that these are people that would not go to vote... When the revolutionary moment has passed, how does one convey all these energies of the different political factions (left, LGBT, etc) again so that people can go to vote again in the sense that they can participate actively in the political life of the country.

PG: There are moments in all countries that are revolutionary. The right-wing loses power, the economies lose power. If there is someone or people on the other side about to lead these uprisings that can be positive. In the case of this film and Chile in recent years, this was a revolt with results, so this is a relative change. Things are basically the same. It is very complex to analyse the roots of a revolution. In the whole world, we are in a moment of apathy which is very dangerous and complicated. We are in a difficult period...

Q: Thank you very much for your amazing movies. I know that many people in Chile have voted: no for the new constitution in Chile. This is difficult to believe if you follow the events and watch your movie. From what we have seen we feel that people want change in Chile and this is a very fundamental thing and in the end, they voted with a no. How can we understand this, why?

PG: When I was there filming, the impression was that a revolution was going to happen. There was a very big mass movement, and the women played a central role in this. There is no other film in which women's opinions are featured as much as in my film. The role of women in Chile is very interesting.

Q: We want to know how you remove your emotions right now in your vision as a documentarist.

PG: I believe that we are experiencing a very complex situation at the moment. In the case of Chile, for many years and many decades, there has not been a political movement, but when this revolt happened, there were no leaders to take control of this movement and its course. There are no small committees to channel this energy. We face a movement in Chile that does not have representatives who can lead it. It is spontaneous without a clear ideology and lacks competent leaders. There are leaders, there is a precedent, but they have no political experience. In this way, there will be the possibility of a new revolution.

NS: Thank you so much Mr. Guzmán, we do not want to keep you longer but if you would like to stay with us, we will turn to Lena Ulbricht and speak about contemporary Chilean politics.

ŞE: Lena, thank you so much for being with us. One of the first questions I would like to ask is in relation to the protests in 2019. When the film starts off, we learn that the spark is essentially the rise in transportation fees, and all the speakers in the film are women, and we really focus on the women's movement and this feminist perspective. Can you perhaps explain a little bit about this composition and how the women's movement eventually came to the forefront and how this is at the moment as well?

LH: Thanks so much for the very kind introduction. I was also very much stimulated by the feminist movement in Chile and other Latin American countries. It is important to understand that this is the spirit of the time, which means that it may be different from a situation that we had 30 years ago, where there was not one feminist movement. You have an ecological movement, an indigenous rights movement, and a socialist movement, but the feminist forces are stronger than all of these movements, and I think this is why some people say that in Chile, but also in other places,

women are taking forward the different movements. For example, there are very important activists in the anti-extractivist movement, an environmentalist movement, and many of them are women. I think this is something that makes these different movements grow together. Of course, there is also the movement that is mainly feminist, which is very visible and very strong, but this is something that brings them together and gives the entire movement this force that we saw in the movie.

NS: ... What went wrong during this constitution process and what can happen right now, are there any preparations at the moment?

LH: I would be very happy to explain because I think it is super important for all those who do not follow Chilean politics on a daily basis to understand that this movie would probably have been significantly different if Patricio Guzmán had waited another year to finish it. The result of the referendum was really crushing for the Chilean progressive minds because the rejection of this constitution, which would have been one of the most progressive in the world - in terms of women's rights, indigenous communities' rights, and environmental rights - came as a total shock. It was rejected, and not by a close margin, but by 60% against about 30% approval. This outcome was a shock to many Chilean expats as well because they are usually pretty progressive. For example, in Berlin, we had about 70% approval of the new constitution. It is important to know that it failed and that we are in the midst of a new constitutional process, which looks different. It will be finished soon, actually, as we are on a fast track, and in November, we will have to vote on a new proposal. In December, we will know once again whether we succeed or not, but the situation is very different. The current assembly that is elaborating on the new proposal looks different in the sense that there are many more representatives from the political institutions, including elected deputies. However, the right-wing dominates the assembly, and there are concerns that we might get a constitution that is worse than the Pinochet constitution. Many things can happen in the process, but the outlook is really difficult. If you ask me what went wrong, sorry if this is long, but it is a complex question and we have been in a depression for a year trying to understand what is happening and how to continue from here. Many things have been written about it, and there are certainly many stories about what went wrong. One of the first explanations was that the media system is just rotten, monopolistic, and dominated by right-wing media monopolies. There is also a disconnect between the population and the professional politicians, who seem to show mistrust in the text that was being elaborated. It was a very

progressive constitution, but it was also super long and detailed, and there seemed to be a mistrust that this could actually be put into place. There was some kind of mistrust in the professionalism of the constitution. Of course, it is lamentable. I think the constitution is the beginning of a process of implementation in any country, no matter how long it is. But that is something we have to acknowledge too, and there are many fears. The entire campaign revolved around fears, and one of them was that the country would be divided because it implied a lot of decentralisation and territorial autonomy. Even people living in those territories did not really trust it. This is something interesting because Germany is also a federal country, and the population itself and most of the surveys say that they do not like that, they want a unitary country and the same rights and access for everybody. So I think it is super difficult to have something as abstract as ideals and visions in the constitution and then the very concrete expectations of the people. Many people did not vote in their own interest but were afraid of losing what they already knew.

NS: Thank you.

ŞE: When you talk about fear, as you mentioned earlier, you touched on the role of the media, and Nicole, one of the characters in the film, talks about the cameras becoming targets of the police. Since you work on digital technologies, network societies, and the film does not really

touch upon it, I was curious to know what role digital technologies and social media, in particular, played during these protests? What kind of presence was there, and was a lot of the organisation of protests done through these networks? Maybe you can talk a little bit about that.

LH: Yes, I would be happy to, of course. It's always complex. Both campaigns heavily used digital media. In the first days or maybe in the first half a year of demonstrations, especially before the pandemic hit when people were really on the streets and the movement started gathering against power, social media seemed to be an opportunity for progressive ideas to find an audience, gain visibility, and mobilise all those who might be affected but were not aware of the mobilizations. For example, independent newspapers and newly created groups heavily relied on social media, so that was somehow productive. There was also hope to use social media as a counterbalance against the public and hegemonistic media, which tends to be right-wing. However, what happened is that social media is supposedly agnostic, but it works very well for right-wing activism. So, social media in itself is not progressive; it is just an amplifying platform. During the campaign concerning the constitution, social media was super powerful in spreading disinformation. For example, a very common topic was that the new constitution would create a radical feminist society or a super indigenous society, where white males would have no rights. This disinformation still worked because people were afraid that things would change drastically. The same fear was seen in discussions about education, health systems, and pension systems. While there was a consensus in Chile that these privatised systems had terrible effects, when the new draft of the constitution was presented, people felt that they did not really understand what they were voting for and what they would get. Thus, they preferred to stick with what they knew rather than what was different. Social media is always a mixed bag; we project many hopes towards it, we use it, but it can also pave the way for a backlash.

NS: Regarding social media and common tools used during these revolts, each time we show a film here, we find something very familiar. The other day, there was a film about Myanmar, and for instance, people were using saucepans again. This common language of revolts, can you comment on this? The feminist song that came out of Chile and spread all over the world, what do you think about this?

LH: Growing up in Germany with my Chilean background, I have this European perspective towards Chile. When I go there, I can also look at it from a distance. The artistic expression of

this protest was just amazing and mind-blowing. Talking with fellow Chilean or German-Chilean activists here, it is true that Chilean protests are entirely different experiences compared to German protests. The colours, the reasons, whether you dance, whether you invent new songs and slogans for every demonstration, this is the Chilean way. In Germany, we might march with the same slogan for 100 years. So it was super creative, and it also took up a lot of symbols and practices known from the Allende times. For example, the Casarola, an evergreen, was used in the protests. There have been other protests and outbursts, like the penguin revolutions when high school students wear uniforms and resemble penguins. So, there have been a lot of new artistic expressions of social discontent, but there is also continuity, and of course, the relationship with the authoritarian forces, as seen clearly in the movie.

Q: I am just wondering, because of also seeing Santiago in this movie; I used to spend a lot of time in the south of Chile in Araucania, and for me, it is like two different countries, actually. I was there during the time when Bolic was the president and after. I would speak with people about their opinions and their opinions about the new constitution, and it was very strange because most of the people I got to know there were against it. Then I saw Santiago, young people, and social media. It was like two different worlds. Maybe there is an explanation for that.

LH: Chile is a highly polarised country between the left and the right, the urban and the rural, and between different zones, so what you observe is something that we all observe. Everybody who has a family in Chile will probably have, in their own family, a Pinochetista and somebody who supported Allende, somebody who was tortured, and somebody who was torturing. We live with this tension, and it makes the predictions of election outcomes very difficult. There is also a rumour that these predictions were not very accurate because there were strategies, maybe of the right-wing - it is a rumour - but not everybody would say whether they were really voting in favour or against the constitution because the prediction prognosed a greater margin, not this huge rejection. Then there is also, as I mentioned, this fear that the country would be divided, and it's true that everywhere else outside Santiago, they say: we don't have the metro, we don't have a subway, and this is symbolic of their feeling of being disadvantaged. Only the capital gets the metro, and the other regions don't, so there might have also been this fear that once the territories or different regions get more autonomy, it would not be more beneficial to them, but it would rather be to their detriment.

ŞE: I have one question, which I think is important, especially in the grander scheme of what we are doing here with the "Gezi, Ten Years After" festival, is to talk about the role of the diaspora and remote engagement in such big uprisings and events happening in home countries. We are far away; what kind of role do our communities here have, and what do we do? Do we protest? How can we support the movements that are happening on the ground without risking anyone's lives but also by amplifying them and maybe creating a pressure point from our locations? I would just like to hear your ideas on that and your experience also, maybe.

LH: Yes, I probably don't have 20 minutes to answer, so I will try to be super short, also because you guys are tired. To break it down, maybe there are two things that we did. Probably more can be done, but what was really amazing to see - and I have compañeros sitting here, my

comrades in arms - Clau, Mai, Tejerco - we did a lot of stuff together, and we came together, and we got to know each other. Mai and I were even working together, but we had not really talked, and then when Chile happened, we became friends and started working together. One thing was really to start supporting the movement with the means that we had. That would mean solidarity parts, to gather money to send equipment, for example, for these emergency helpers, just for them so they could provide themselves with the gear that they need to protect themselves during their work, or money that we would send to families of indigenous communities, political prisoners, because there are many. That was one thing. Also, raise awareness here about what was going on in Chile. But then after time, we felt it is also time to discuss the responsibility of this society here and how it is implicated in what is happening elsewhere. So then I would say it fed more into a reflection, on the one hand: on the German responsibility because the German government also trains Chilean police forces, so try to investigate the relationships. Another thing that we also did is to better connect with other Latin American activist groups here in Berlin. And I would say that this fed into... It was not only us, but these many different activists from Colombia, from Mexico, from Guatemala, we started reflecting more on how this society is also sexist and racist and extractivist, and so to bring the discussions from there to here, maybe also learn from their way of expressing means, like using art. We did this choreography so many times in different manifestations, also one on the 8th of March, for example, which is the Women's Day Demonstration here in Berlin. We really also try to bring this conflict to the conflicts that we have here, and this also touches, for example, the living conditions of undocumented migrants in Berlin, in Germany, because the stuff they fight for - nothing of this is really solved well here. It is something that we can discuss and fight for here, and where we can support each other from that point. This time for many of us, I think, was a super productive time even though Guzmán said it twice: it left no traces. I would not say that. It did not give us the constitution we wanted, but I think it left many traces and also a positive experience for many of us. I think if it happened once in my lifetime, it might happen again, right? We don't know.

NS: Then we send our solidarity to the Chilean people and the students, and the people who are in prison... We thank you all and Lena.

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